

AGGREGATORS ON THE ELECTRICITY MARKET OF UKRAINE**Denysiuk S.P.,***Dr. Sci. (Engin.), Professor, Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute, Kyiv, Ukraine*<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6299-3680>**Bielokha H.S.,***PhD (Engin.), Associate Professor,**Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute, Kyiv, Ukraine*<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4277-367X>**Ushchapovsky K.V.***Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Member National Commission for State Regulation in the Field of Energy and Utilities,**Kyiv, Ukraine*<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6662-2244>**Abstract**

With the increasing implementation of smart grids with distributed energy resources and active consumers, there is a need for aggregators. The article examines the issue of aggregation and the specifics of its implementation in Ukraine. The introduction of a new type of activity (aggregation) is a positive trend, both for the energy system of Ukraine and for electricity market participants who will join the aggregated groups.

Keywords: aggregator, renewable energy sources, electricity market

Introduction. The introduction of Smart Grids and Demand Response technologies is a response to the large-scale transformations that have occurred in the energy sector over the past decades, in particular, the transition from traditional fossil fuel generation to renewable energy sources (RES). To include “green” generation in the energy balance, it is necessary to have additional reserves – capacities in the power system that can quickly provide the necessary electricity at the time of a decrease in renewable energy generation, which requires additional investments in the construction of new highly maneuverable generation. Another way is to learn to manage demand, adapt to peaks and troughs in generation.

Horizontal electricity trading (peer-to-peer trading) is becoming more widespread – the sale of electricity from renewable sources between market participants using a contract with predefined terms that govern the automatic execution and completion of the transaction, carried out either directly between market participants or indirectly through a third party market participant, such as an aggregator. [1, 2].

In European practice, the concept of an aggregator has been introduced - an entity that represents a set of small consumers or small generation on the market [3, 4]. Its task is to communicate with the dispatch center in order to use the capabilities of these groups for balancing the system. The aggregator, together with the consumers and/or generation it represents, will ultimately receive a fee for its balancing services.

Along with the importance of the role of consumers in electricity markets, the Preamble to the Directive on internal market rules (Directive (EU) 2019/944 on common rules for the internal market for electricity) notes the critical importance of aggregators. These intermediaries allow consumers to more easily sell their managed loads and the electricity they generate and/or store in storage facilities on the market. Consumers should be able to fully benefit from all the services of such aggregators. This directive requires EU Member

States to define models for the participation of aggregators in all electricity markets, including the ancillary services market and the capacity market, in a way that encourages consumer participation in demand management. It should be noted that according to the provisions of Directive 2012/27/EU: an aggregator is a demand service provider that combines several short-term consumer loads for sale or auction on organized electricity markets.

The definition of aggregators is included in the 4th Energy Package [3]. At the same time, the Directive on electricity market rules contains both a definition of the market function of aggregation and a definition of an “independent aggregator”:

– “aggregation” means a function performed by a natural or legal person that combines multiple consumer loads or generated electricity for sale, purchase or participation in an auction on any energy market;

– “independent aggregator” means a market participant that performs aggregation and is not affiliated with the supplier of a particular consumer.

Article 2 of the Directive on renewable energy (Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources) defines peer-to-peer trading of renewable energy as “the sale of electricity from renewable sources between market participants using a contract with predefined terms governing the automatic execution and completion of the transaction, carried out either directly between market participants or indirectly through a third party market participant, such as an aggregator”.

An aggregator can help in better integration of RES by providing both demand and supply flexibility services to the grid. Demand-side flexibility is provided by aggregating demand-response resources or energy storage to meet grid requirements. Supply-side flexibility is provided by optimizing electricity generation from flexible resources such as combined heat and power plants, biogas plants, etc., as well as the use of energy storage units. Therefore, aggregators are agents

that combine and manage distributed energy resources and their flexibility to create value from optimized participation in the electricity market. The advantages of using aggregators [1, 5]:

- aggregators will participate as new stakeholders in the future operation of the energy system and electricity market trading;
- a distributed control scheme for managing distributed energy resources (DER) is an advantage over simple centralized or decentralized coordination;
- the development of electricity grid infrastructure and related regulations should consider a broad modeling of the aggregator concept.

The aggregator interacts with each customer through an energy management system installed at the customer's facility [1, 5, 7]. The energy management system is a smart metering platform with management and control functions to support the active exchange of services between smart grid stakeholders, such as end users, aggregators and retailers. The aggregator's architecture itself defines the interaction with consumers, TSOs and electricity markets [1, 6, 7]. The aggregator relies on a centralized hierarchical management and control structure to optimize and control consumer participation in electricity markets and reserves.

Legislative support for aggregators in the energy sector of Ukraine. On July 27, 2023, the Law of Ukraine No. 3220-IX "On Amendments to Certain Laws of Ukraine on the Restoration and "Green" Transformation of the Energy System of Ukraine" (Vidomosti Verkhovnoi Rada, 2023, No. 82, p. 301) that approved the introduction of the following definitions into the legislative field of Ukraine:

- aggregator - an independent aggregator or other participant in the electricity market who carries out aggregation activities;
- aggregation - an activity in the electricity market carried out by a business entity related to the association of electrical installations intended for the production and/or consumption, and/or storage of electrical energy for the purpose of buying and selling electrical energy, providing auxiliary services and/or balancing services in the electricity market;
- aggregated group - participants in the electricity market whose electrical installations are included in one aggregation unit and are aggregated by an aggregator;
- aggregation unit - a set of electrical installations intended for aggregation;
- independent aggregator - a market participant that carries out aggregation activities and is not affiliated with the electricity supplier and/or universal service provider of the consumer whose electrical installations are aggregated by such market participant.

Before the legislative changes, the definition of "aggregator" was contained only in the Transmission System Code, where its content was focused on the role of executing TSO (Transmission System Operator) commands [8].

According to Article 30-2 of the Law of Ukraine "On the Electricity Market", aggregation activities in the electricity market are subject to licensing in accord-

ance with the legislation, except for cases where a business entity – a participant in the electricity market has a license for the production and/or storage, and/or supply of electricity to consumers, and/or for conducting economic activities to perform the functions of a guaranteed buyer. An independent aggregator does not have the right to carry out activities for the supply of electricity to a consumer under an electricity supply contract to a consumer.

In this case, the relations between the aggregator and other participants in the aggregated group are regulated by the contract for participation in the aggregated group. The essential terms of the contract for participation in the aggregated group are determined by the market rules. The aggregator may aggregate one or more aggregation units. The aggregator is the party responsible for the balance of all electrical installations included in its aggregation unit, with the exception of electrical installations intended for consumption by consumers who purchase electricity from another market participant engaged in the supply of electricity to the consumer.

The aggregator is prohibited from carrying out activities related to the transmission and/or distribution of electricity, transportation and distribution of natural gas, and performance of the functions of a market operator. The aggregator purchases and sells electricity on the electricity market in accordance with the provisions of this Law, market rules, day-ahead and intraday market rules, and other regulatory legal acts regulating the functioning of the electricity market. The aggregator provides balancing services and/or ancillary services in accordance with the provisions of this Law and market rules. It is also noted that the aggregator has the right to:

- 1) carry out the purchase and sale of electricity on the electricity market;
- 2) timely and in full receive funds for the electricity sold by it in accordance with the concluded contracts on the electricity market, for ancillary services and balancing services;
- 3) receive access to information on activities on the electricity market in the manner and to the extent determined by the market rules, the rules of the day-ahead and intraday markets and other regulatory legal acts regulating the functioning of the electricity market.

However, the aggregator is obliged to:

- 1) comply with the licensing conditions for conducting economic activities on aggregation, other regulatory legal acts regulating the functioning of the market;
- 2) prepare daily electricity schedules in accordance with the volumes of purchased and sold electricity and provide them to the transmission system operator in accordance with market rules;
- 3) provide market participants with the information necessary for them to perform their functions in the electricity market
- 4) be a provider of balancing services in cases specified by the market rules;

A consumer has the right to join an aggregated group without the consent of the electricity supplier of

such consumer. However, an electrical installation intended for the production and/or consumption of electricity and/or an energy storage installation may be part of only one aggregation unit. An aggregation unit may not include an electrical installation intended for the production of electricity with an installed capacity exceeding 20 MW.

Based on legislative norms and requirements for activity, the aggregation unit will be considered, primarily by the Transmission System Operator NPC Ukrenergo, as one separate generation unit, and not as a large number of individual participants. In essence, it is a virtual power plant that will participate in balancing the power system, providing auxiliary services, etc. This will allow the aggregator and participants of the aggregated group to receive additional profit.

The aggregator manages and is responsible to the transmission system operator for the implementation of the transmission system operator's schedule and commands with respect to its aggregation unit. The aggregator must ensure the ability to manage electrical installations included in one aggregation unit separately for each area of commercial accounting of the network.

Payment for electricity transmission and distribution services for aggregated power plants is made by the owners of these power plants or their electricity suppliers. Contracts for participation in an aggregated group may provide for penalties (fees) for the exit of a power plant from the aggregated group. Such penalties (fees) must be proportional and must not exceed the direct losses and/or costs of the aggregator as a result of the termination of the contract, including the cost of services already provided under the contract. Penalties (fees) cannot be applied to household and small non-household consumers.

At the same time, having the above-mentioned licenses and carrying out aggregation activities (without obtaining a special license) - the market participant must comply with the licensing conditions for aggregation.

The aggregated group, in terms of its structure and model of association of participants - is the most legally close to the already known phenomenon on the market - the balancing group. Just as in the balancing group one entity is responsible for the balance (the one who created such a group), so in the aggregated group - the aggregator carries out activities for the aggregation of electrical installations of all participants of such a group. That is, the aggregated group is an association of market participants into one aggregation unit (virtual power plant) - in order to obtain additional profit, due to the optimization of the purchase and sale of electricity, the provision of auxiliary services and balancing services for NPC "Ukrenergo" [8–10].

The obligation to ensure the ability to manage electrical installations assumes that the aggregator has an appropriate software product (software) that allows remote control of electrical energy generation/storage units [9, 10]. The cost of these software products on the market is extremely high. This indicates that the "entry threshold" for aggregation activities is much higher than for electricity supply or trading activities.

The aggregator is also the party responsible for the

balance of all participants in the aggregated group, except for consumers who receive electricity from other electricity suppliers. Thus, the aggregated group can be considered as a balancing group in the electricity market, but with greater opportunities for the purchase and sale of electricity and the provision of auxiliary and balancing services. The law also contains restrictions on the capacity of electrical energy generation installations that may be part of the aggregated group. The specified limitation is no more than 20 MW of installed capacity for each individual generation unit.

For example [8–10]: Several power plants are combined into an aggregated group, which is administered by an aggregator. The combination is carried out on the basis of a corresponding agreement on participation in the aggregated group. The aggregator purchases the generated electricity, resells it and is the party responsible for the balance. The aggregator also provides Ukrenergo with auxiliary services and performs dispatching commands. The aggregator receives the profit from such activities and pays the agreed payments to the participants of the aggregated group.

Implementation of aggregation principles in the energy sector of Ukraine

"National Energy Company "Ukrenergo"" (NEC "Ukrenergo") (the transmission system operator of Ukraine, a member of ENTSO-E, with the functions of operational and technological management of the Unified Energy System of Ukraine (UES), transmission of electricity through main power grids from generation to distribution networks, as well as the administrator of commercial accounting and the administrator of settlements on the electricity market of Ukraine) is interested in increasing competition in the balancing market (BR) and the ancillary services market (ASM) in order to expand balancing capabilities, and therefore, increase the reliability of the UES operation [10].

NPC "Ukrenergo" is considering the creation of the first virtual aggregator of small and household energy storage in Ukraine, which could combine them into one large energy storage system and enter the ancillary services market [10]. In order to provide 1 MW of loading-unloading services, it is necessary to collect 3–4 MW of installed capacity of small and household energy storage (500–1000 owners to gain a guaranteed 1 MW).

As an example of the formation of aggregated groups in Ukraine, we note the achievements of JSC "Energy Company of Ukraine" and Kness Smart Power [11, 12].

Joint-Stock Company Energy Company of Ukraine (JSC "ECU") launched one of the first aggregated groups in Ukraine, which offers services for operational and commercial management of distributed generation facilities [11]. Services for electricity producers include load planning, dispatching, purchase and sale of electricity, and optimization of imbalances. It is taken into account that an aggregated group is an association of small and medium-sized electricity producers (up to 20 MW) for joint production and sale of electricity. By combining their capacities, the group members operate as a single "virtual power plant" managed by the aggregator company. Such consolidation

creates a number of benefits for small producers that they cannot receive in the case of independent work.

In turn, Kness Smart Power is part of the Ukrainian group of companies KNESS, [12]. The main area of the company's activity is the unification of electrical installations designed for the production, consumption, and storage of electrical energy for the purpose of buying and selling electrical energy and providing auxiliary services for balancing in the electricity market. Kness Smart Power is a licensed aggregator and operates in the territory of all distribution system operators.

Kness Smart Power intends to carry out aggregation activities as a party responsible for the balance of all electrical installations included in its aggregation unit, with the exception of electrical installations intended for consumption by consumers who purchase electricity from another market participant engaged in the activity of supplying electricity to the consumer. It is determined that the agreement on participation in the aggregated group must include: the procedure for calculating the volumes and cost of electrical energy for the settlement of imbalances; the procedure for calculating the cost of the balancing group administration service; instructions for downloading data from the market management system (MMS) by the Balancing Group Participant; the form of the act of purchase and sale of electrical energy for the settlement of imbalances for the settlement month; the form of the act of acceptance and transfer of work performed (services provided).

Main directions of development of aggregators in the energy sector of Ukraine. According to the results of the analysis, we can distinguish the following main directions of development of aggregators in the energy sector of Ukraine.

1. General issues of aggregation of demand for electricity

1) Demand management aggregators in the national electricity market;

2) Functions and tasks of aggregators: (1) from the consumer side (flexibility, incentive system, formation of rational load profiles); (2) from the energy market side (sale of flexibility in the energy market, provision of balancing services for DSOs);

3) Aggregators and flexibility: flexibility services provided by the aggregator, flexibility platforms; local flexibility markets; the need for aggregation to ensure flexibility for small customers, supply and demand for the small consumer aggregator; the aggregator as a coordinator of consumer flexibility; overcoming barriers to the adoption of local energy markets and flexibility;

4) Aggregator platforms for local energy communities of consumers, prosumers and producers.

2. Aggregator forecasting mechanisms:

1) Aggregator forecasting mechanisms: market prices; production costs (fuel price forecasts); production volumes (short-term forecast models for wind and solar installations);

2) Forecasting demand and supply in local energy communities, in particular in energy cooperatives.

3. Economic aspects of aggregation:

1) Aggregator as a new link in the value chain for

RES projects that need to enter the market; demand response aggregator for RES integration and customer acquisition (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats);

2) Economic aspects of aggregation: aggregator business models; types of aggregator business models (independent aggregator model, dependent aggregator model, retailer model);

3) Aggregator as a market agent for electricity production, aggregation contracts to guarantee the profile of the electricity sales price for the producer in exchange for a service fee (per sold MWh);

4) Aggregation of demand in energy cooperatives, whose members jointly own and/or manage RES facilities;

4. Modern models and approaches to implementing aggregation

1) Model and structure of aggregators; aggregator architecture, interface between aggregator and prosumer;

2) The role of the electric vehicle aggregator in the electricity market;

3) Economic methods of stimulating consumer participation in the aggregation of demand for electricity;

4) Regulatory and legal regulation of the formation and provision of aggregators' activities in the electricity market;

5) Issues of electricity metering in the context of using aggregators in the electricity market

Conclusions

Based on the legislative norms and requirements for activity, the aggregation unit will be considered, primarily by the Transmission System Operator "NPC "Ukrenergo", as one separate generation unit, and not as a large number of individual participants. In essence, it is a virtual power plant that will participate in balancing the power system, providing auxiliary services, which will allow the aggregator and participants in the aggregated group to receive additional profit.

However, the current definition of aggregators in Ukraine is imperfect compared to the European vision, its presence does not create opportunities for the existence of aggregators as full-fledged participants in the electricity market. In order for aggregators to start operating in Ukrainian conditions, additional regulatory prerequisites are necessary, in particular: development and consolidation at the legislative level of a new definition for aggregators; consolidation of provisions on non-discrimination of independent aggregators; development of technical documents and standards for the participation of aggregators in organized electricity markets; creation of regulatory documents that will allow regulators to receive remuneration for their own services.

Today, it is important to work out the mechanism for the creation and development of such aggregators that ensure the unification of electricity consumers, renewable energy facilities and the accumulation of electricity for the purpose of joint participation in the wholesale and retail electricity market. Therefore, the development of both scientific foundations and regula-

tory, methodological and legal support for the functioning of aggregators in Ukraine, taking into account the current state of the Unified Energy System of Ukraine and the regulatory and legal support of the energy sector of Ukraine, is relevant.

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